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ANALYSIS OF SUBSEA EQUIPMENT IN DEEP WATER AND ITS ECONOMIC VARIATION

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INTRODUCTION

The process of selecting project alternatives for oil field developments in deep waters is an important step in ensuring the success of the fluid extraction and processing enterprise. As each reservoir has different characteristics and properties, develop a preliminary and objective assessment of the options for the relevant project. The number of wells, their positioning, length, diameter of production pipelines, wet or dry Christmas trees, subsea equipment associated with the Stationary Production Unit (UEP) including technological analysis and system flexibility, to maximize the chances of selecting the development arrangement most suited to the characteristics of the reservoir.

The subsea production system to which this study refers is about the layout in which the interconnection lines, positioning of the Christmas tree, control and injection system that will be on the sea floor are designed. During this process, alternatives will be generated, that is, indications of use or not of equipment, types of platforms, submerged pumping systems, among others.

Thus, the present study aims to understand the construction and installation of arrangements for extraction and lifting

of petroleum fluids considering the subsea system in deep waters and to develop the possible conceptual configurations of the production system for an oilfield project. The purpose is to meet the maximization of oil recovery with a basic cost assessment in general that includes CAPEX (capital investment) and OPEX (operating cost) analysis.

METHODOLOGY

The present study will be of the case study type with research of the comparative type where will be studied all at alternatives viable for use of the subsea production arrangement.

O development in a project in system in production offshore , involves a body multidisciplinary, each stage require a level in knowledge advanced at the what it says respect to the materials and services addressed, being then in Dice real obtained in form in Query at companies of this branch. O gift field petroleum demand one solution for enable The exploration and production in Petroleum at the sea considered currently viable and a new method for your Implementation. Most specifically if refers The one settings From equipment submarines proposal for four wells in Petroleum and is based at evaluation gives rate in variation in CAPEX (

capital expenditure) and OPEX (operational expenditure)

RESULTS

1. Description of Field in manu

Ofield in manu It is a field fictitious although adequate The reality. IT IS an offshore reservoir , located 100 km off the coast of Rio de Janeiro with volumes recoverable in between 15 The 20 thousand barrels in Petroleum per day (bpd) in each well, oil that is of good quality with 33°API, that is, relatively light, as it is basically constituted by alkanes and a percentage of 15 to 25% in cycloalkanes, in addition in gas Natural associated. That field it has four wells The one blade water in 1,000 meters, O project It is estimated for 15 years of production and the price per barrel used in the calculations must be US\$ 111.25 as reported by Jornal Nicomex Notícias in November 2012

Any pit in Petroleum The to be perforated he must to satisfy The some parameters minimums, then for the project to be economically viable, the cost with the implementation From several equipment necessary for the exploitation of the deposit it has to be advantageous. As a main parameter, for the economic evaluation of the project, the estimation of the volume of the deposit stands out. O field producing in your capacity maximum he can to arrive up until 80 thousand bpd.

2. Data From Equipment submarines

The construction of Table 2 was carried out based on the data and values for the period of September 2012 at the Rio Oil & Gas event – Rio de Janeiro January - Brazil and through in interviews with professionals of sector. For continuation of that study he was researched O cost in each equipment submarine justifying and evaluating the rate of change of your CAPEX and OPEX to the data in the table consist of estimates, analyzes with the professionals interviewed.

TYPE IN EQUIPMENT SUBSEA	OCCUPATION	SPECIFICATION	COST
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Tree in Christmas Wet	Allow the well control in production or injection.	IT IS constituted per a block wrought, where they are mounted at valves in manual lock and hydraulics;	CAPEX \$ 800,000.00 OPEX \$ 200,000.00 Total \$ 1,000,000.00
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Flowline	Carry oil and/ or gas from wells to the manifolds , carry oil and/or gas from manifolds up until The platform, carry Water and other substan- ces of platfor- ms of produc- tion, through manifolds _ in injection, up until The head in pit in injec- tion.	IT IS The pipe in head return from the well, through the which The mud raisin for The sieve oscillating. He can to be also the pipe per Where pass the oil or gas produced.	CAPEX \$ 6,000,000.00 /km OPEX \$ 6,000,000.00
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FPSO	It is used for exploita- tion, storage and flow gives production for ships tank.	Platform with Format in ship, it has 6 mouths for riser and has maximum ca- pacity for 200 thousand bpd.	\$420,000,000.00 The unity or Rent: \$ 150,000.00/ day and OPEX \$ 26,000.00
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Manifold Subma- rine	Get together in form balanced and controlled production in several wells in only one only pipe in production.	IT IS constitu- ted per piping arrangement, set of valves block, valves in control in drainage and subsystems monitoring, control and interconnection. arrangement, set of valves block, valves in control in drainage and subsystems monitoring, control and interconnec- tion.	CAPEX \$ 8,000,000.00 OPEX \$ 2,000,000.00 Total \$ 10,000,000.00
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Ship reliever	Used for transport of Hydrocar- bons.	Ships in two hooves, a It is O own hull of ship and the other is the wall of tank in Petroleum.	\$ 350,000.00/ day
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Table two: Cost in Each Component of System

Source: Search FMC Technologies, Technip – interview 2012 and Magazine Petroleum and Energy - 2011

The petroleum engineer often uses specific software to simulate at interrelationships in between you equipment submarines and to evaluate at best possibilities for if to take one decision. These tools make possible characterize and simulate O process in production in a reservoir The leave in information relative to the Dice of place, representing O positioning of the wells and simulating the flow of fluids in this reservoir virtual, aiming get information what make possible optimize The production.

Alternatives in Project

At alternatives The be evaluated were analyzed and developed calculations mathematicians for to determine at possible options in arrangements productive through of which The production can to be carried out in form economic.

The implementation of the subsea arrangement type in the Manu field will be elaborate from a comparison between the four alternatives offered. The specification of the best system for the project will be based on the rate in variation in CAPEX and OPEX calculated.

Such challenges take The need in development in new methods what allow design, with The minimization in scratches and costs O best scenery at the processing in oil and gas.

Alternative THE

For The first alternative use one platform type FPSO connecting the four wells, two flexible risers of 660 meters each, two PLETS, a manifold for junction of lines of production. For the PLEM and The Christmas tree uses up four outfits each. As for the flowline are four ducts also, being what each a give me 495 meters. At valves in block will be operated per a remotely Operated vehicle (ROV).

In Figure 12, a planned subsea arrangement scheme is presented. for the alternative a.

Figure 12: Flowchart of Alternative A

Source: Built by author

Analysis economic gives Alternative THE

Expected to recover fence in 60 thousand bpd, with O plan in proposed development and peak production will be reached in 2014, at 80 thousand bpd.

This analysis will be based on the purchase of an FPSO for 15 years of operation with storage capacity of 900 thousand barrels of oil, being so O ship reliever only will make O offloading two times per month, justifying O rent diary for The operation. O ROV it will be bought.

THE Table 3, show The specification of CAPEX already with O number in equipment calculated and O time of project estimated.

Table 3: Specification of CAPEX for The Alternative THE

Description	The amount	capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	4 in 495 meters	US\$ 11,880,000.00
FPSO	1	US\$ 420,000,000.00
manifold	1	US\$ 8,000,000.00
Ship reliever	Rent two times per month	US\$ 126,000,000.00
PLEM	4	US\$ 14,400,000.00
PLET	two	US\$ 1,300,000.00
riser	two in 660 meters	US\$ 5,280,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: built by author

O investment It is referent The need in disbursement for The acquisition of the item and the operating cost is related to the operating and maintenance. O value in OPEX considered at Table 4, express O cost operational Yearly for O system in study.

Table 4: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for The Alternative THE

Description	capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christma	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 360,000,000.00
FPSO	US\$ 390,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
PLEM	US\$ 24,000,000.00
PLET	US\$ 4,500,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: built by author

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative THE, according shown at Table 5.

Table 5: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative THE

Total CAPEX	US\$ 593,960,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 565,740,000.00
Total General	US\$ 1,159,700,000.00

Source: built fur author

At analysis in cost note what O investment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 593.96 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 565.74 millions at the Final in all O project.

In one year of production, the field will produce 21,900 barrels of oil soon, O project It is economically viable, then O barrel it will be sold The US\$ 111.25 thousand totalizing US\$ 67.58 billion.

Alternative B

At Monday alternative use also one platform of type FPSO to receive the production of the four oil wells and two risers of 660 meters each, which in turn is connected to a manifold. O use of a PLEM in

that model it will be for to receive you ducts in Petroleum From four different wells and connect to other production pipelines that will be connected directly to manifold, of this form there is one reduction in amount in investments and also the costs to be spent on the project. use four Christmas trees and the help of an ROV. It is important to note that two flowlines measure 330 meters and you others two measure 220 meters.

In Figure 13, a planned subsea arrangement scheme is presented. for the alternative B.

Figure 13: Flowchart of Alternative B
Source: Built fur author

Analysis economic gives Alternative B

Inside in three months, you four wells producers in Petroleum will be interconnected to the FPSO, in order to gradually increase the production of the field. In wake up with calculations mathematicians, The FPSO go to introduce one production in 60 thousand barrels in oil equivalent per day at the first quarter, soon after your production increase for 80 thousand bpd for what so be reached the purpose of project.

In this stage will be performed at activities in calculation and analysis in sensitivity

of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative B, The analysis economic will be made based on the specification of the equipment and implementation of the same, taking into account the purchase of an FPSO and an ROV. The ship reliever it will be rented per a period in 15 years old.

THE Table 6, show The specification of CAPEX already with O number in equipment calculated and O time of project estimated.

Table 6: Specification of CAPEX for The Alternative B

Description	The amount	capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	two in 330 meters	US\$ 3,960,000.00
flowline	two in 220 meters	US\$ 2,640,000.00
FPSO	1	US\$ 420,000,000.00
manifold	1	US\$ 8,000,000.00
Ship reliever	Rent two times per month	US\$ 126,000,000.00
PLEM	1	US\$ 3,600,000.00
riser	two in 660 meters	US\$ 5,280,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: built by author

It will also be taken into account that for each item presented there is a existence in information in investment and cost operational in 15 years old. O value of OPEX considered in the Table 7 expresses itself the cost operational for you equipment.

Table 7: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for The Alternative B

Description	capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christma	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 360,000,000.00
FPSO	US\$ 390,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
PLEM	US\$ 6,000,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: built by author

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative B aiming

at comparison with data from other alternatives to be made at the elapse of this study, according shown at Table 8.

Table 8: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative B

Total CAPEX	US\$ 576,580,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 543,240,000.00
Total General	US\$ 569,980,000.00

Source: built fur author

At analysis in cost note what O investment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 576.58 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 543.24 millions at the Final in all O project.

In addition from that, equal The alternative previous, O horizon in time in implantation It is in a year for recovery in all O your capital invested. This model presented an evolution of the costs spent during the project, when step what no has in two PLETS and three PLEMs becoming so O design with other viable alternative.

Alternative Ç

One turn what The depth gives Water decreases significantly to far away in 100 km gives coast, reaching 1000 meters in depth, The platform spar buoy it went out as one option.

This system has some advantages over the FPSO, such as excellent behavior in severe seas, its performance is great in blades water deep and ultra-deep, it has great capacity in storage.

In that arrangement it will be implemented in addition gives platform type spar Buoy , two risers in 660 meters each a, four trees in Christmas, three flowlines in 220 meters and one of 330 meters that will be directly connected to the manifold to join of lines of production.

In Figure 14, a planned subsea arrangement scheme is presented. for the alternative C.

Figure 14: Flowchart of Alternative Ç
Source: Built fur author

Analysis economic gives Alternative Ç

For this alternative, a Spar Buoy platform will be purchased . To the Underwater inspection an ROV will also be purchased. the relief ship will be rented twice a month so that offloading can be done , as the maximum storage capacity of Spar Buoy platform is 1000 barrels in Petroleum. That alternative will have a flow rate in 60 thousand bpd us its first five months and 80,000 bdp by the end of its operation. No with no production stoppage during the 15 years of operation, this platform can to produce up until 401,500 thousand barrels in Petroleum.

IT IS fundamental The individualization of specifications in each subsea equipment used in the project and its due associated costs to time in operation estimated for to guarantee transparency and safety during The life productive of field.

THE Table 9, show The specification of CAPEX for each equipment already with

The the amount you same calculated it's the time from the project estimated for 15 years.

Table 9: Specification of CAPEX for The Alternative Ç

Description	The amount	Capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	3 in 220 meters	US\$ 3,960,000.00
flowline	1 in 330 meters	US\$ 1,980,000.00
manifold	1	US\$ 8,000,000.00
Ship reliever	Rent two times to month	US\$ 126,000,000.00
riser	two in 660 meters	US\$ 5,280,000.00
spar buoy	1	US\$ 340,000,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: Built by author

Among the financial math questions was developed the table 10, Where resume at conditions for O project consolidate your capital in operation and maintenance to far away of period in 15 years old at the field in Manual

Table 10: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for

The Alternative Ç

Description	Capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christmas	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 276,000,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
spar buoy	US\$ 318,750.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: Built by author

The process of selection of equipment for the development of a subsea arrangement in a deep water oil field is a step important ensuring O success of project.

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative C at Table 11.

Table 11: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative C

Total CAPEX	US\$ 492,320,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 453,168,750.00
Total General	US\$ 945,488,750.00

Source: built by the author

At analysis in cost note what investment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 492.32 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 453,168 millions.

Alternative C has as a return up to its fifth year of operation more in US\$ 65,213 billion being so one option in arrangement submarine economically viable.

Alternative D

Spar Buoy platform is also used. for to receive The production of four trees in Christmas what they are connected to manifold per four flowlines being a measuring 330 meters and you others measuring 220 meters. Important highlight what in this alternative in arrangement the submarine uses two PLETs that make the interconnection of the flexible duct with the rigid duct what in turn measures 660 meters, thus facilitating the use of the ROV what it will be bought. O use in four PLEMs it will be for to secure The operation of system serving for turn on O set submerged in ducts. Through in valves operated fur ROV in that equipment O set in ducts has The option in to be isolated and O pipeline closed at the case in a blowout, per example.

In Figure 15, a type of subsea arrangement is presented that can be implemented in the Manu field with its maximum flow from second year of

operation, arriving The 80 thousand bpd.

Figure 15: Flowchart of Alternative D
Source: Built fur author

Analysis economic gives Alternative D

Spar Buoy platform is used for the field production, with the advantage of flexibilizing the production capacity charge at the deck, being that O first concept of that type in unity of developed float. as the field of Manu is found 100 km away gives coast no having possibility of fluid produced for the platform to be flowed through an oil or gas pipeline, according to the flow of the system submarine O process in offloading it will be done only two times to month thus ruling out the possibility of purchasing a relief ship, Where That vessel has as activity main drain The production in Petroleum or gas of units producers offshore .

THE Table 12, show you spending in expenses in capital, or be, service debt due to the capital invested to purchase the equipment that will be necessary in the implementation from the project already specifying O CAPEX in each a with O time in service calculated for 15 years old in operation.

Table 12: Specification of CAPEX for The

Alternative D

Specification	The amount	capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	3	US\$ 3,960,000.00
flowline	1	US\$ 1,980,000.00
manifold	3	US\$ 8,000,000.00
PLEM	4	US\$ 14,400,000.00
PLET	two	US\$ 1,300,000.00
Ship reliever	1	US\$ 126,000,000.00
riser	two	US\$ 5,280,000.00
spar buoy	1	US\$ 340,000,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: Built by author

For to evaluate O return financial in projects it will be then required know O cycle total in life expected for The production, O price The to be practiced at sale in products, at quantities what must to be produced for each product from the initial phase of pre-operation, normal operation, increase in production, period of maximum production and decline in production, spending on expenses in CAPEX and spending with at expenses in OPEX

Table 13: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for The Alternative D

Description	Capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christmas	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 276,000,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
PLEM	US\$ 24,000,000.00
PLET	US\$ 4,500,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
spar buoy	US\$ 318,750.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: Built by author

Really, CAPEX and OPEX no are methodologies. O first anything is more than a British expression for expenditure and/or investment of capital thus being the sum of all investments in resources

and the purchase From equipment necessary for to maintain a environment operational in production, being O second It is O what if refers to the costs and expenses operational.

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative D

Table 14: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative D

Total CAPEX	US\$ 508,020,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 481,668,750.00
Total General	US\$ 989,688,750.00

Source: Built by author

AtanalysisincostnotewhatOinvestment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 508.02 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 481.66 millions for all O project.

Alternative D has as a return in four years of operation more than US\$ 69.95 billion being so one option in arrangement submarine economically viable.

ANALYSIS IN RESULTS

The case analyzed is a project to develop a field of oil that has a range of four alternatives, each with a scale in production different, for O development of same. So comes up the possibility of the field being developed to operate in medium or large scale, being one assignment of engineer in Petroleum The search for the excellent production. When there is only one only alternative available to engineer, no there is a choice to be made as to the scale of production. But, having more than one option in arrangement submarine, O professional raisin The to have most flexibility, already what, becomes possible choose which best alternative

in wake up with O scenery in question. O appearance in most in one option in arrangement productive only he comes add value to project.

You values used at the study were Dice real in queries and researches in companies what act in the branch oil. However, the relationship between the FPSO and shuttle ship rental values were based on contracts real what have duration in 15 years old.

For to analyze all at alternatives, aiming to meet you main requirements to start the operation in the Manu field, an analysis will be carried out separated for each layout introduced.

Analysis in Results for The Alternative THE

One time that the value in a project is based on your capacity in generate flows in boxes futures, or be, generate dividends, at alternatives in investments can be compared only if financial events are measured in a same time and, one turn what at operations in investment or financing has features in a spacing in flows in Cashier over time.

O value of money at the time It is The reasoning gives analysis in results and It is The base for at measurements in profit for select investments.

Generally, the economic evaluation of petroleum projects is carried out by quite in mathematical calculations of Which are obtained you main indicators economic.

In the evaluation of Exploration and Production projects, it is important that the equipment selected be shown in the phase in technical decision on to the decision-making process of how the oil fields should be laid out, for that It is important what you concepts be clear and integrated with O process in management from the deposit.

For The first alternative he was introduced O cost in US\$ 1,159 millions

for The phase initial of project, that result includes The purchase and O rent in equipment submarines and in subsurface.

For this alternative, the field development plan reached the your objective, in your second year in production O field in manu will be producing 80 thousand barrels in Petroleum per day.

Through gives Figure 16, It is possible to view in manner simplified The production for O field in manu for the alternative THE.

Figure 16:
Graph of Field Production by Alternative A
Source: Built fur author

You results obtained for The evaluation of price equivalent The US\$111.25 thousand O barrel in Petroleum resulted positive, indicating what Oproject It is highly lucrative.

Analysis in Results for The Alternative B

In this section, you main parameters used for The generation From results are presented for The Alternative B.

THE reservation what it is being considered behaves, in average, O equivalent The four hundred millions in barrels in Petroleum, being able be variations of up to 50% in this value, that is, the volume of the reserve considered he can be understood in between two hundred and six hundred millions in barrels in Petroleum.

For O price of Petroleum, it is considered

The amount in cent and eleven dollars per barrel being O price current, subject The volatility in 25%.

As mentioned earlier, there are four scale options many different for O development from the project, being what in your third year of useful life, the production of the field increases from 60 thousand bdp to 80 thousand bdp reaching so The your productivity maximum as shown at Figure 17.

Figure 17:
Graph of Field Production by Alternative B
Source: Built fur author

For all O investment in maintenance and operation it was considered as being a year O time for The first use of OPEX

By the results found, it is noticed what in this analysis O values spent at phase initial of p project it will be in US\$ 569.98 millions, value that starting from the pre supposed what no go there was none fact unexpected what end taking place The stop in production.

By observing the two alternatives that expose the results found, it is verified that the value of the project of the second alternative is reduced, compared with the first alternative, there is a withdrawal of three PLEMs and two PLETs where there is evidence of some changes regarding the safe operation of the submarine system. Choosing to invest in this type of operation has become any less attractive.

still notice obtaining in a result as to the profitable part of two alternatives. THE first alternative in has maximum production of field soon at the Your first year in operation While what The Monday alternative only will reach this productivity in your room year, It's fair what there is one difference partner economic in between you two models. Important highlight what The Monday option also It is treated as being one alternative in project economically viable.

Analysis in Results for The Alternative Ç

The investment in the purchase from a Spar Buoy platform Visa add value to the project so that the top From risers stay sheltered inside of the platform cylinder protecting them from waves and currents where the It is made about you ducts generally It is larger.

For that type in platform O your system account with high grade in stability, thus becoming inherent in having its center of care above your center in gravity, with The help from lower tanks that reduce the distance between the keel and the same, creating an independence of stability with your system in anchoring. Although for that type in operation It is required one technology new in addition gives your installation to be difficulty fur size gives your super structure.

The cost of capital invested in the first phase of the project is US\$945.49 billion as calculated in item 6.5.2 with a return in 15 years of operation US\$ most in 764.03 billion, making so That alternative economically viable.

O field in manu will reach The your production maximum The leave of your fifth year in operation, as shown at Figure 18. THE your production

grow upgradually, after this rapid expansion to its peak, the extraction of oil tends to remain at 80,000 bdp until the end of the project's useful life, as the As the pressure of the deposit increases and the flow of oil inside it is facilitated for the voltage superficial From pores (CAMPBELL , 1997).

Figure 18: Graph of Field Production by Alternative C
Source: Built fur author

IT IS possible O use of that type in arrangement at the field studied if no wereits complexity regarding the installation of the Floating Unit 1000 km from the coast. The choice of the best grade of steel to be implanted in the structure, adequacy From tanks, in between others.

These Law Suit in project and consultancy shall to have what idealize concepts in installation what you can toast one installation fast and efficient within the parameters required by the different security agencies, making it like this an important disadvantage compared to a platform FPSO type.

For ends in Comparison, O model most lucrative up until O gift moment is the alternative in study, but that doesn't mean it's the best to be implanted at the field in Manual

Analysis in Result for The Alternative D

To to determine O best layout in a system submarine, you costs ever

has a paper important. THE profitability It is a From main goals of investment in a project, in way to earning capacity isin extremely important.

O cost total It is most in US\$ 508.02 millions It is how much to development of field in your phase initial what has as expense O CAPEX For maintenance and operation From equipment he was calculated annually and your cost stayed in most in US\$ 481.66 millions up until O Final giveslife useful of project. whereas the production initial will be 21,900 thousand barrels and after Oits secondyear there is an increase to 29,200 thousand barrels, a value calculated with the maximum capacity of the field, as shown in Figure 19, the project in study will give one profitability in most in US\$ 819.62 billion at the Final in 15 years old of operation.

Figure 19: Graph of Field Production by Alternative D
Source: Built fur own

Although that result no It is plywood due The installation gives platform spar buoy Where he must to be considered shipments cumulative in the transport phase of some members of the structure generating fatigue until the field in Manual

At Table 15, are presented you values in return in investment in 15years old for many different values in price of barrel, of values current The minors values, comparing with O price in a environment

economic stabilized at the international market for reduction in scratches financial of enterprise for 4 scenarios of price in Petroleum which considers the value current of Marketplace The minors values in a environment economic stable, reduction of price up until The price of barrel in US\$ 33.25.

Table 15: Values in Return in Investment for 15 years old

Years in Production	Production in Oil (bbl)	Total Production in Barrel in 145 years old	Variation of Price of Barrel (US\$)
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	112.25
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	80.25
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	50.25
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	33.25

Source: Built by author

With analysis in these information you can to notice what you two first items are the most give profitability to company due to price of barrel per to be most high, soon concludes what at latest two alternatives are not viable, prices per barrel lower than US\$ 50.25 for the use of production system.

CONCLUSION

In order to analyze the different flows in the oil reservoirs, needs graphics at the excel, Where show clearly what you results of four alternatives presented reach The your productivity maximum to throughout the life of the project. Flow guarantee is viable for all options varying only at profitability of field.

considering what us fields in

Petroleum Where The installation in infrastructure is quite expensive, the use of FPSO systems ends up being one alternative quite attractive. In one situation as it is in what O place is far from the coast and operating in deep waters, the installation of a platform spar buoy no he can to be justified due to your complex installation process thus making the possibility of using an FPSO being O type in platform ideal for O project.

THE platform FPSO has as advantage about at others platforms O fact that it doesn't have to be a purpose-built structure, one can easily be converted in a ship oil tanker, offering itself as support in case in locomotion making so a ship in transport, again reducing costs and providing one structure effective to sector offshore .

With base us results found, you can conclude what The leave In this study, some advantages and disadvantages were identified for the four development and production scenarios, where we can highlight a larger flexibility for mitigate O type in arrangement submarine of field in manuand it was found what The Alternative THE requires a larger CAPEX at the value in US\$ 593.96 millions and one larger safety at execution From works offshore.

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